

A Meta-Analysis of Scholarly Journals in Library and Information Science Theses: A Case Study

Onwubiko Emmanuel Chidiadi

Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ikwo, Nigeria
ORCID: 0000-0001-9386-4972
onwubikoemma@yahoo.com or emmabikos@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

One major issue faced in many university libraries, is the bibliometric analysis of scholarly journals cited in research reports by students especially the postgraduates who are ardent users of these scholarly journals as they form bulk of their research sources because of the recency, authenticity and reliability of their information and this remains a veritable tool for effective management of scholarly journals especially in the area of selection, acquisitions and weeding. This therefore is a bibliometrics study of scholarly journals cited in postgraduate library and information Science theses/dissertations of selected federal government universities in Nigeria from 2015 to 2023. The study applied descriptive survey design with a sampled population of 296 which form the total number of accessible masters' theses and doctorate dissertations submitted within the period under study. The researcher self-designed checklists validated by three experts from the department of measurement and elevations of Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria were the major instrument used in obtaining data needed for the study. Data collected were analyzed using frequency and simple percentile while the results were presented in tables. The outcome of the study among others revealed that the most cited scholarly journal titles were within the zone one (1) constituting the core journals cited by postgraduate students of library and information science of the studied university using Bradford's Law of scattering. The result also shows that academic journals cited were published mainly in the US, UK, India and South Africa. Based on the findings, it was recommended among other things that for effective application of bibliometric analysis as a functional tool for effective journal management, staff of serials unit most partner documentation unit as to ensuring proper bibliometric analysis of journals submitted to the library by every department as this can be used as a guide for the unit to identify the core journals for selections, acquisitions and also as a guide for total serials collections maintenance and that university librarians should expose staff of the serials units to series of in-house training on how to apply bibliometric analysis in evaluating scholarly journals and proper classifications of scholarly journals based on their bibliographic entries

Keywords: Bibliometric Analysis, Academic Journals, Library and Information Science, Theses, Postgraduate, University Library

1. INTRODUCTION

Scholarly Journal or Academic Journal as the case may be though two words which stand for the same thing is explained as information source that contains scholarly published articles usually about research written by experts (scholars) in the field of study. As a custom articles in these publications go through a peer-review process, which means other experts (peers) on the topic of the article weigh in on the quality of the article and the research it presents as well as the article's importance in their field of study (Cullen, 2020). In the same vein, Victor Valley College Library (2024) which also describes it as scientific journals, or peer reviewed journals defines it as a periodical that contains articles written by experts in a particular field of study which are intended to be read by other experts

or students of the field, and they are usually much more sophisticated and advanced than the articles found in general magazines.

Highlighting on the characteristics of scholarly journals, Victor Valley College Library (2024), reveals that they are published for a purpose so as to communicate the results of recent research in the field of study covered by the journal, Scholarly journal contains articles that reflect a systematic and thorough study of a single topic, often involving experiments or surveys and occasionally publish review articles that summarize the current state of knowledge on a topic, has unique appearance as they lack the advertising, colorful graphics, and photographs found in popular magazines as articles are often lengthy, begin with an abstract, and may include graphs, tables, or charts. As well as the name of the author or authors and a list of references, they are written by the person(s) who did the research being reported. When more than two authors are listed for a single article, the first author listed is usually the primary researcher who supervised or coordinated the work done by the other authors; articles submitted to scholarly journals are evaluated by an editorial board and other experts before they are accepted for publication. This evaluation, often called "peer reviewed," is designed to insure that the articles published are based on solid research that meets the normal standards of the field of study covered by the journal as well as articles in scholarly journals are usually in-depth and contain an advanced vocabulary, since the authors use the technical language or jargon of their field of study. Articles are not written for the general public in that the authors assume the reader already possesses a basic understanding of the field of study.

It against this backdrop that many professors will require student researchers or scholars to utilize scholarly sources because they are more credible than articles published in popular magazines or on most websites same applies to many instructors who assign research papers or projects and require students to read articles published in scholarly journals.

Ultimately, academic journals or scholarly journals which are periodical publications in which scholarship relating to a particular academic discipline are published in every university library are one of the most important and useful collections as they serve as permanent and transparent forums for the presentation, scrutiny, and discussion of research. It reliability is built on the fact that they nearly universally require peer review for research articles or other scrutiny from contemporaries competent and established in their respective fields. These all important research sources have further been professionally defined as publications in any medium issued in successive parts at regular or irregular intervals, usually having numerical or chronological designation and intended to continue indefinitely (Purdue University ,2021. Morteza, 2021 & Onwubiko, 2016).

The importance of scholarly journals to researchers cannot be underestimated as researchers depend on them on current researches and outcome as they consult journal articles where recent and current researches and their result can be found. It is against this backdrop that Idhalama and Obi (2019) posit that scholarly journals are important publications in academic and special libraries due to the currency of information they contain as well as Komolafe, Gbotosho and Odewole (2020) who opined

that journals are important to students and researchers because they contain the most current and relevant information that can be used for academic and research purposes. It against this backdrop that their management in libraries especially academic libraries is seen as very paramount as researchers need current information and this can only be accessible and effectively utilized only when they are properly managed for users to have access to the information contained therein. Effective management of journals has become so imperative with the escalating costs of journals and the dwindling available library budgets which necessitates the judicious use of available financial resources and invariably manage the acquired information resources including journals. This was also affirmed by Ogunnuga (2013) who reported that there is an increase in the relevance of journals management by libraries due to reduction in library budget and the need to provide current library information materials such as journals and this has made journal management to be among the most challenging routines in academic library.

Ultimately, research is accompanied by a written account of the research procedure, an outcome known as research reports. In academics, at higher degrees, a research report is a document that presents the author's research findings and is submitted in support of candidature for a degree or professional qualification (Fleetwood, 2023). It is the main idea of one's research and is normally the culmination of a candidate's research; submission of the research report represents the completion of the final requirement for the postgraduate degree being pursued. The research reports for the purpose of this study include thesis and dissertation. Thesis is a proposition, a reasoned argument, which involves a comprehensive research on a theme connected with the specialty of a candidate for any of certain academic degrees, while dissertation is a formal discourse, written or spoken, a treatise, especially an original piece of research together with course work where research predominates over course work and constitutes not less than two-third of the total credit load (Nworgu, 2015).

Considering the place of graduates research reports and that postgraduate students are most users of scholarly journals as they form the hub of their research information sources, it is imperative to analyzing their citations as to establishing the titles and sources of journals used and research has shown that one effective way to achieve this, is through bibliometrics analysis. Bibliometrics analysis has been rightly define as an attempt to quantitatively assess the academic quality of journals or authors by statistical methods such as citation rates, librarians therefore need not to look in the negative direction when the issue of bibliometric analysis is discussed as it is seen as a functional tool for harnessing the needed information materials by researchers like graduate-students. This is built on the premise that through bibliometrics analysis of journals in theses or any other research report, the librarians will come to terms with the actual journals that are being utilized by researchers (Ahamer, & Kumpfmüller, 2014).

Furthermore, bibliometrics studies is concerned with the examination of citations made to a work as a way of evaluating of publications, authors, institutions or even a geographical entity as well as the use

of quantitative analysis and statistics to describe patterns of publication within a given field or body of literature. It therefore, uses citations in scholarly works to establish links in that many different links can be determined, such as links between authors, scholarly works, journals, fields, or even between two or more nations. The implication is that bibliometrics analysis is very useful to finding out the influence of a particular work and permits researchers to see how frequently the work has been cited in articles and are an invaluable tool for any literature review [Library and Information Science Education Network (2022)]. In addition, bibliometric analysis is used to determine collections' used by students in academic libraries and analysis serves as invaluable tool in the assessment of library collection which the journals are part [Anunobi., Nwakwuo, and Ezejiolor, 2010].

Bibliometrics has also been explicitly defined as the statistical analyses of books, articles, or other publications in which the analyses are used to track author or researcher output and impact, calculate journal impact factors and data collected through the process can also be visualized to understand publication relationships. On the impact metrics that can be measure with bibliometric data, it was highlighted to include article/book citation impact from which academic impact of particular works, such as journal articles, conference proceedings, and books, can be measured by the number of times they are cited by other works, journal citation impact with which impact of particular academic journals can be measured by the number of times their articles are cited and where they are cited and researcher citation impact which brings at bay the number of works a researcher has published and the number of times these works have been cited which in turn can be an indicator of the academic impact of an individual researcher (University of Illinois Library, 2024). This implies that bibliometric analysis can help identify areas of weakness within journals collections (Rethlefsen, 2007).

This approach as noted helps clarify both the information needs of researchers and what should be contained in a research library collection and sine, librarians have usually been challenged in the ability to generate, organize, make accessible, analyze and evaluate information resources in a way the researchers would find useful. Consequently, librarians have recognized bibliometrics analyses as a very useful technique for proper analysis and evaluation of research outputs, leading to its growing acceptance for research evaluation and a useful in investigating the coverage of library acquisitions and for research evaluation [University of Illinois City Library, 2021].

In the use of Bradford's law to ascertain core scholarly journal cited in any research report, Bradford's law 1934 states that documents on a given subjectll is distributed (scattered) according to a certain mathematical function so that a growth in papers on a subject requires a growth in the number of journals/information sources. The number of the groups of journals to produce nearly equal numbers of articles is roughly in proportion to $1:n:n^2$, where n is called the Bradford multiplier which is a constant. The law explains that journals in a single field can be divided into three parts, each containing the same number of articles:

- i) A core of journals on the subject, relatively few in number, that produces approximately one - third of all the articles;

- ii) A second zone, containing the same number of articles as the first, but a greater number of journals, and
- iii) A third zone, containing the same number of articles as the second, but still greater number of journals.

This implies that journals displayed in table 1 are core journals of library and information science though few in number but produced highest number of articles cited in the postgraduate theses and dissertations of the four universities studied . This is followed by journals in zone 2 with greater of journals but producing lesser articles cited in the postgraduates' research reports in library and information science of the four universities studied.

It is pertinent therefore to state that despite the accrued gains of bibliometric analysis in library acquisitions and journals management as well as the prominent role scholarly journals play in meeting up the information needs of graduate researchers and other scholars, there are evidences of inadequate and some cases, lack of analysis of journal citations of graduate-students theses not only in libraries and information science but in other fields of study in the past years in most universities especially those of developing countries like Nigeria. The worse scenario is that there is no data showing that these universities are providing bibliometrics analysis of references in theses generally and to best of the knowledge of the researcher no research has been carried out in this aspect of body of knowledge therefore there is a gap in knowledge that needs to be filled.

It is in view of this, that the researcher felt there is need for a study on bibliometrics analysis of academic journals in postgraduate theses in particular as a functional tool for effective journal management in university libraries with a view to creating the desired awareness for serials librarians in universities to embrace bibliometrics analysis as veritable tool for evaluating journals collections and by so doing enhancing effective academic journals management using accessible theses submitted from 2015 to 2023 to four federal universities in Nigeria offering Library and Information Science to postgraduate level as case in point. This period was chosen because it was considered adequate as research reports were readily available and current as to ascertaining the present trend in journal citations.

The main purpose of this study therefore is to carry out a bibliometric analysis of academic journals cited in postgraduate theses. Specifically the following objectives are intended to be achieved;

1. To determine titles of scholarly journals on Library and information science cited by graduate students in their theses in the universities studied,
2. To ascertain countries where these scholarly journals are published.(geographical location) and,
3. To determine the most cited library and information journal titles based on Bradford Law

2. METHODOLOGY

The study applied descriptive survey design with a sampled population of 296 which form the total number of accessible masters' theses and doctorate dissertations submitted from 2015 to 2023 in federal government universities in Nigeria offering Library and Information Science at higher levels that covered the period of study. They are; Bayero University, Kano (BUK), University of Port Harcourt (UNIPORT), University of Ibadan (UI), and University of Nigeria, Nsukka, (UNN). The researcher self-designed checklists were the major instrument used in obtaining data needed for the study. With the checklists, 9528 journals citations were analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency, percentage and range and data presented in tables.

3. PRESENTATION OF DATA

Table 1: The cited Library and Information Science journal titles in the theses and dissertations, place of publication and Ranked List based on Bradford bibliometrics Law of Scattering

S/ N	Journal Title	BUK		UNIPORT		UNIBADAN		UNN		Total	Pop	Rank
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%			
1	Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)	124	25	119	23.89	130	26.1	125	25.1	498	USA	1 st
2	International Information and Library Review	87	25	60	17.25	94	27.01	107	30.74	348	UK	2 nd
3	African Journal of Library, Archives and Information Science	72	24.08	64	21.4	77	25.76	86	28.76	299	South Africa	3 rd
4	The Journal of Academic Librarianship	70	25	55	19.64	73	26.07	82	29.29	280	Netherland	4 th
5	International Journal of Library Science (cpub)	62	25	50	20.16	65	26.21	71	28.63	248	India	5 th
6	IFLA Journal	55	22.27	64	25.91	60	24.29	68	27.53	247	USA	6 th
7	College and Research Libraries News	62	27.56	56	24.89	50	22.22	57	25.33	225	USA	7 th
8	International Journal for Digital Library Services	50	22.22	56	24.89	63	28	56	24.89	225	India	7 th
9	Journal of Education for Lib & Info Sc	45	21.02	53	24.77	56	26.17	60	28.04	214	Canada	9 th
10	The Electronic Library	54	25.84	40	19.14	55	26.32	60	28.7	209	UK	10 th

International Journal of Engineering and Future Technology

11	Library Herald	43	21.71	49	24.75	55	27.78	51	25.76	198	India	11 th
12	South Africa Journal of Library and Information Science	52	26.26	41	20.71	50	25.25	55	27.78	198	South Africa	11 th
13	The Information Technologist	46	24.73	36	19.35	49	26.35	55	29.57	186	South Africa	13 th
14	Annals of Library and Information Science	52	27.96	40	21.5	46	24.73	48	25.81	186	India	13 th
15	Library and Information Science Research	49	26.34	43	23.12	46	24.73	48	25.81	186	Netherland	13 th
16	Nigerian libraries Journal of the Nigerian Library Association	50	26.88	40	21.51	47	25.27	49	26.34	186	Nigeria	13 th
17	Nigerian Library Link	48	27.12	39	22.03	41	23.16	49	27.68	177	Nigeria	17 th
18	International Information and Library review	48	27.12	35	19.77	44	24.86	50	28.25	177	Netherland	17 th
19	Journal of Librarianship	44	24.86	40	22.6	48	27.12	45	25.42	177	UK	17 th
20	New Library World	37	20.9	44	24.86	46	25.99	50	28.25	177	UK	17 th
21	International Journal of Librarianship and Administration	42	24.71	40	23.53	46	27.06	43	25.29	170	India	21 st
22	Library Management	35	21.21	30	18.18	47	28.48	53	32.12	165	UK	22 nd
	Grand Total	1227	24.63	1099	22.06	1288	25.85	1368	27.46	4982		

*Key>Pop=Place of publication

Summary of Journal titles cited in each Bradford Zones

Zone	No. of Journals	No. of Citations	% of Journals	% of Citations
1	22	4976	10	52.22
2	23	2441	11	25.62
3	166	2111	79	22.16
Total	211	9528	100	100

4.0. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The outcome of this study shows that library and information journal titles cited in library and information science graduates research report within the year under study were 22 in number which include, Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal), International Information and Library Review, International Journal of Library science, African Journal of Library, Archives and Information Science, The Journal of Academic Librarianship and IFLA Journal among others (see table 1). The utilization of these professional journal titles may not be far from Komolafe, Gbotosho and Odewole (2020) assertion that journals are important to students and researchers because they contain the most current and relevant information that can be used for academic and research purposes.

The study also discovered that Library and information science journal titles cited were published in countries which are USA, UK, South Africa, Netherland, India, Nigeria and Canada. This finding affirms the definition of bibliometrics studies as one concerned with the examination of citations made to a work as a way of evaluating of publications, authors, institutions or even a geographical entity (Fleetwood, 2023).

From the result of study, the rank list of journals in the field of Library and Information Science reveals that journal citations cited by researchers are scattered among 211 journals. Among them, Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal) ranked the first for being cited more number of times with 498 of total journal citations of 4982, followed by International Information and Library Review (IILR) with 348 citations, African Journal of Library, Archives and Information Science -299 while cpub International Journal of Library Science ranked 4th among others. The first 44 journals in the rank list contribute nearly 71% of total journal citations. According to Bradford Law of scattering, the 22 journals in zone one are considered as core journals followed by those in zone two (Bradford,1948). The ranking list of journals therefore is a practical tool that helps librarians to select journals of maximum utility in relation to their coverage of new and important literature in a particular subject area (Chamani, 2013). Garfield also suggested that rankings developed from total citation counts could be a variable in developing core journal lists (Garfield, 1977).

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the outcome of this study therefore, one can deduce that bibliometric analysis of scholarly journals is a veritable instrument if applied will enhance effective journals management in any university library. The obvious being that by identifying the journal titles that are most cited and further identify the most cited titles of such journal and place of publication, the librarians is placed in a better position as to knowing areas to be considered while selecting scholarly journals for acquisitions and how to organize them based on researchers preference for easy accessibility and utilization. Hence this buttresses the assertion that the obvious placement of bibliometric analysis is that it is used to determine collections' used by students in academic libraries. Suffice it to say, that bibliometric analysis serves as invaluable tool in the assessment of library collection (Haycock, 2004). To this end the following recommendations are made:

- I. In the first instance, for effective application of bibliometric analysis as a functional tool for effective journal management, staff of serials unit most partner documentation unit as to ensuring proper bibliometric analysis of journals submitted to the library by every department as this can be used as a guide for the unit to identify the core journals for selections, acquisitions and also as a guide for total serials collections maintenance.
- II. The librarian should expose staff of the serials units to series of in-house training on how to apply bibliometric analysis in evaluating serials and proper classifications serials based on their bibliographic entries.
- III. Since one of the primary roles of university libraries and librarians is information creation and documentations, it behooves the university librarian to ensure that all submitted theses are documented and analyzed in line with the lay down collections development policy of the library.
- IV. The university management should formulate policy that will promote bibliographic control of theses and dissertations. This is based the on the experience of the researcher that none of the university libraries could at a glance state the number of postgraduate reports available. The art of bibliographic does not only help in organizing knowledge, but will also help postgraduate students know areas covered so far in their fields and areas that need to be researched upon

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